

CHEMISTRY OF PROTEOLYSIS

BY SUDHINDRA NATH SEN

Explanations have been put forward on the basis of the dipole moments of C—H, C—C, N—H bonds for the enzymatic breakdown of protein molecules.

The observed fact that proteolysis is favoured in the vicinity of an aromatic ring, is suggested to be due to the property of this group to induce polarity in the neighbouring carbon atom. Conditions that would fail to induce polarity, would retard the process of hydrolysis.

The function of enzyme is to form an activated complex with protein and then to ionise the —CONH— linkage by induced polarity. This complex reacts with H^+ and OH^- until equilibrium is established. The lowering of energy of activation in the process of proteolysis is accounted for by the work done in bringing the (OH^-) within the range of action of the peptide linkage against the potential of the field.

Presence of amino-acids of opposite rotatory power to that met with in nature inhibits the action of pepsin. This is due to a change in the planer position of different groups which probably fails to induce polarity at —CONH— linkage. The effect of steric hindrance appears to be energetic rather than geometrical in nature.

Enzymes are a group of organic substances of highly specific nature whose functions are to direct chemical reactions in particular directions. It is now recognised that most of them are complex systems made up of a number of components of which the protein moiety determines the specificity of the enzyme. Enzymes do not and cannot influence the equilibrium point of any reaction. They only serve to decrease the time to reach such a state. Thus their function is to reduce the energy of activation for the particular process in which they are acting. The velocity and temperature quotients are specific for a particular enzyme and substrate, but are different for various proteins acted upon by the same enzyme or for a particular protein treated with different enzymes. Lineweaver (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 403) has shown that enzymic reactions have a lower temperature coefficient than the corresponding non-enzymatic reactions. In the process

of hydrolysis of protein by enzymes, the sum total effect is the addition of water molecules to the protein with the formation of lower breakdown products. The nature and the mode of the reactions and the part the enzymes play are not fully known. Northrop (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1919-20, 2, 595; *ibid.*, 1922, 5, 263) suggested that the ionisation of the protein molecule is an essential characteristic precedent to protein hydrolysis. But the ionisation of a big multipolar molecule, such as a protein, is not well understood unless the site and the nature of ionisation that would lead to hydrolysis, are made clear. In dealing with polar reactions, such as protein hydrolysis, the polarisability of the molecules, and the electrostatic nature of the dipole moments of the co-valent bonds present in it, must be considered, as these play a significant part in predisposing the molecule to act in a particular way. It is intended to discuss in this paper the mechanism of proteolysis in the light of modern electronic conception of organic chemistry.

With the exception of Barendrecht (*Biochem. Z.*, 1924, 151, 363) who supported a radiation theory of enzyme action, almost all authors have postulated an union of enzyme and substrate. Some have favoured the adsorption theory (Willstätter and Waldschmidt-Leitz, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1923, 125, 132; Northrop, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1919, 2, 113, and others), whereas some have postulated a chemical union between enzyme and substrate (Michaelis and Menton, *Biochem. Z.*, 1913, 49, 333; Stearn, *Ergebn. der. Enzymforschung*, 1938, 7, 1; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 970). Tide of evidence is, however, in favour of a chemical union. Since the ultimate product of hydrolysis is not a compound of enzyme and protein, the protein-enzyme complex, after its formation and specific activation, must dissociate itself from enzyme and breakdown products of protein. Two cases may arise here: (i) The enzyme may be more strongly bound to the reactant than to the activated complex. Here the release of enzyme will cause an increase in entropy. (ii) The enzyme is more strongly bound to the activated complex and the process of separation will involve a decrease in the entropy of the system. Stearn (*loc. cit.*, 1938) found that in most cases the entropy of the protein-enzyme system decreases. This goes to establish an union between enzyme and substrate and this complex molecule, which is still a protein, in turn becomes activated. The activation of a multipolar molecule like protein must be followed by the development of polarity within the molecule. This increase in polarity may be further augmented by the proximity of the polar molecules of the enzyme in the complex. The sum total effect of augmentation may rise to such an extent as to give an ionised molecule instead of merely a molecule of increased polarity. If the energy content of a polyatomic molecule be so increased as to be capable of reactivity, which otherwise it does not possess, it may be assumed that the molecule has passed through a constitutional change. This change is expressed by a modification of the valency formula conventionally assigned to its unexcited form. The usual assumption with respect to activation is that of opening the double bonds. This is preferred because the energy increase attributed to this transformation explains the energy of activation (*cf.* Staudinger, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 3035; Flory, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 241). The dipole moments (in 10^{-18} e.s.u.) of the principal linkages that occur in any peptide chain are C—H, 0.2; N—H, 1.5; C—C, 0; C=O, 2.5. Since ionisation will only take place at the site of maximum polarity, the peptide linkage (—CONH—) becomes the site of ionisation and maximum reactivity. Since the activation of water molecule is an essential feature

in any enzymatic hydrolysis, as shown by Battelli and Stern (*C.R.A.C.Sc.*, Geneva, 1922, 37, 65), the mechanism of proteolysis, subsequent to activations may be taken as the addition of polar groups of H^+ and OH^- to the ionised protein molecule, which then breaks into products of lower molecular weight. Thus the whole process may be represented in short as follows :—

Addition of H^+ incurs no difficulty. It differs from all other ions in having no electron either in nucleus or inside and in presence of other ions or molecules there is nothing to prevent it from penetrating the electron-shell of the first atom that it meets until repelled by the positive charge of the nucleus. It will remain there provided there are two unshared electrons in whose orbit it can wrap itself. The addition of OH^- is, however, not so easy. Although it is facilitated by electron attracting groups created in the molecule by way of activation, work has to be done in bringing (OH^-) group through the potential of the field. The lowering of energy of activation in a process by the foreign molecule of enzyme is entirely accounted for by the work done in bringing the OH^- against the potential of the field. Thus the conditions that are to be initiated in the substance before the reaction proceeds are :—

- (i) ionisation of the reagents, (ii) ionisation of the reactant or alternatively the ionisation at the double bond, (iii) formation of co-valent molecule and then
- (iv) conversion of co-valency into electro-valency to neutralise all electrical charges.

All these reactions need not, however, proceed independently and consecutively but may be compiled together so that the energy liberated by one of the operations is available to meet the requirements of another. These conditions are created and requirements are met with by the formation of protein-enzyme complex.

Since a proteinase attacks the peptide linkage, it is reasonable to suppose that it will be able to break the protein molecule completely into amino-acids, but experimental evidences are against this conclusion. Proteinases can hydrolyse protein only to a limited extent. This can be explained as follows. So long as the sites of activation reside in separate portions of the molecule with increased length of the interposed chain, they become independent of each other so that they may be regarded as disconnected mono-valent radicals. Thus we find the specificity of different enzymes—proteinase, peptidase, etc.—though practically of similar nature, depends strictly on the length of the chain they attack.

It is now known that small chemical change in some of the groups of the side-chain or a small alteration in the spatial configuration of the protein might be enough to destroy the enzyme activity. These points are now discussed in detail.

Proteinases are particularly sensitive to the presence and the special nature of side chain

(Bergmann *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 114, 717 ; 1937, 118, 405 ; Fruton and Bergmann, *ibid.*, 1937, 118, 627). It has been shown that for pepsin hydrolysis, if the substrate contains a free COOH group close to the peptide bond, hydrolysis becomes very rapid. Substitution of this COOH so as to give an ' amide ' makes the substrate entirely resistant to the pepsin action. The most favourable combination is of glutamic acid with tyrosine. The substitution of tyrosine with phenylalanine has no altered effect, whereas masking of the COOH group of glutamic acid makes it resistant to peptic hydrolysis. Thus the presence of a free amino group in close proximity to a peptide bond makes the substrate unsuitable for pepsin action. Similarly Hofmann and Bergmann (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 130, 81) have shown that presence of basic amino or guanidino group, but not of free COOH group, is essential for the action of trypsin. If the free amino group is masked, trypsin has no hydrolysing effect. This faculty of differentiation on the part of proteinase can be explained by a combination of the enzyme and the substrate through the different specific groups.

Experimental evidences show that the breakdown of a peptide linkage is much favoured in the vicinity of an aromatic nucleus (Fruton and Bergmann, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 127, 627 ; Northrop *et al.*, *Ergeb. der. Enzymforschung.*, 1932, 1, 302). This preferential hydrolysis may be accounted for by the fact that the phenyl group attached to the carbon atom of the peptide linkage is able to induce polarity in the molecule (*cf.* Burton and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 904 ; *Proc. Leeds Phil. Soc.*, 1920, 1, 421). This increased polarity in the molecule makes it more susceptible to ionic reaction leading to hydrolysis. Direct experimental proof of this type of change in the molecule is as difficult to find as it is to disprove it. The proposed mechanism would, however, lose its significance if it were proved to occur in molecules where polarity does not exist or in the neighbourhood of two polar groups, where the polar effect due to one radical may be taken to be neutralised by the presence of other radical. Experimental evidences show that hydrolysis is greatly retarded in the presence of two tyrosine radicals just on the opposite sides of -CONH- as in the case of *l*-tyrosyl-*l*-tyrosine by pepsin (Fruton and Bergmann, *loc. cit.*). Similarly substitution of glutamic acid by glycine in *l*-glutamyl-*l*-tyrosine, retards hydrolysis.

Proteolytic enzymes are particularly sensitive to one or other optical isomers of amino-acids taking part in the peptide formation. The action of pepsin stops if the peptide linkage contains an unusual amino-acid *i.e.*, amino-acid with opposite optical rotatory power to that met with in nature (Hugonnerq and Loiseleur, *Bull. soc. chem. Biol.*, 1925, 7, 955 ; Iwai, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1924, 136, 173 ; Fruton and Bergmann, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 127, 627). Change in optical rotation is due to a change in the geometrical configuration of the molecule and the failure of pepsin to hydrolyse a peptide linkage containing an unnatural amino-acid, which it otherwise hydrolyses in presence of the natural isomer, may be attributed to a change in the specific configuration of the molecule concerned. An attempt is being made in the following lines to show how the change in configuration affects hydrolysis. The absolute velocity of a chemical reaction is given by the number of molecules reacting per second, which in turn, equals the number of molecules colliding per second multiplied by the chance, that the colliding particles have sufficient energy to react. In a number of instances and specially in enzymic reactions, it

has been found that the reaction values found from the velocity constant of the reaction ($K = PZe^{-E/RT}$) and that obtained from the energy of activation are not of the same order of magnitude. The agreement of two values means that every collision of the activated molecules is fruitful in producing a chemical reaction. Where two methods yield divergent results, steric factors are considered to be responsible for the difference. Stern (*loc. cit.*) found thermodynamically while dealing with enzymic reactions, that enzyme protein complex formation does take place, but hydrolysis is not so great as would be expected. In most cases the entropy of activation of the reaction was considerably more negative than that of the same reaction catalysed by acids. This means that the increase in the reaction rate brought about by the enzyme is not so great as might be expected from the decrease of activation energy.

To visualise the whole picture, a mathematical interpretation is given below. If n molecules of enzyme, by their united effect, reduce the energy of activation from an original value of E_0 to E , each contributing a reducing effect e , then $\Delta E = ne$. Now this will take place only when all the reactive groups of enzyme and protein are properly placed, but the chances that they will do so will be proportional to p^n where p is less than unity. Thus the probability of the reaction, from the relation $K = PZe^{-E/RT}$, although increased by $e^{n/RT}$ is also reduced by p^n . Therefore from these relations (a) $\Delta E = ne$ and (b) $p/p_0 = p^n$, after eliminating n , we find $\Delta E \propto \Delta \log P$. Since Z does not vary from its average value appreciably, the variation in the reaction velocity is dependent either on E or on P or on both. A systematic variation in the energy of activation E has been observed with change in the field intensity F and this again depends on the position of different groups in the molecule (Ingold and Nathan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 222; Hinshelwood and Legard, *ibid.*, 1935, 587). It is also known that the probability factor P depends on the position of different groups in the molecule.

All these go to show that there is a factor which might be a stringent condition of neutral orientation of the substrate and enzyme molecules which interferes with the reaction. It follows therefore that though the polar groups in the molecule primarily dominate the rate of hydrolysis, steric hindrance also plays a great part so that all the collisions are not fruitful in producing a reaction. Hinshelwood and Legard (*loc. cit.*) have shown that reaction velocity is slow not because P is small but because E is not large and in a system where E is large P is always large. Thus a system may become reactive when a large amount of energy is supplied to it, and the factor which normally renders some collisions ineffective in the initial system would have then very little effect. According to the present day conception, the addition of energy to a molecule results in an increase in the vibrational and translational motions of electrons. It is the four pairs of electrons about a carbon atom which are responsible for the direction of valency to the apices of tetrahedron. They are thus also responsible for the optical activity of a particular carbon atom. It is, however, possible that by addition of sufficient quanta of energy, the sphere of action of these electrons can be controlled. This will lead to a high degree of activation which will cause such a high degree of polarisation that the transitional probability factor will tend to approach unity and every collision will lead to a reactive product. Thus steric hindrance which creates the probability factor, appears to be energetic rather than geometrical in nature.

Thus it appears that the retardation in proteolysis when the peptide linkage contains an optical isomer of an unnatural amino-acid is due to the failure to activate the peptide linkage which the enzyme would have done in presence of the natural amino acid. It yet remains to be seen experimentally whether the influence of optical isomers of amino acids in proteolysis could be overcome by the addition of extra energy to the system.

BENGAL IMMUNITY,
RESEARCH LABORATORY,
CALCUTTA.

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